

1 **Trastuzumab resistance features CSNK1A1 activation.**

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6 We studied whole tumor gene expression in humans with pathologic complete response (pCR) or
7 residual disease (RD) following treatment for HER2+ breast cancer to discover gene expression changes
8 associated with, resulting from or causing resistance to treatment with the HER2-targeted treatment
9 trastuzumab (Herceptin). We identified activation of CSNK1A1 in humans whose tumors display
10 resistance to treatment with trastuzumab. Studying whole transcription in HER2+ breast cancer cells
11 engineered to develop trastuzumab-resistance *in vitro* validated this phenomena. CSNK1A1 activation
12 likely supports resistance to trastuzumab in humans with HER2+ breast cancer.
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